

The merger of banks in India: Boon or bane for the Indian economy?

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ABSTRACT

A merger of banks is not a new phenomenon but lately, it has received significant attention in the banking sector. A successful merger of various banks in India, and elsewhere, has attracted the attention of the scholars in the field. The rationale behind such mergers has been hotly debated, and the moot point question remains whether bank merging is good for the economy as a whole. Against this backdrop, this paper attempts to analyze the 'for' & 'against' views on the issue and concludes that the mergers of banks in India positively affects the health of the banking sector & ultimately is helpful to the Indian economy. We argue that the merger of banks brought synergy in the operations of the banking sector primarily in terms of customer reach. In addition, it also provides economies of scale, even though the management change remains a challenge. Similarly, amalgamations also bring relief for the Reserve Bank of India (RBI). RBI can better concentrate its efforts on the supervision of niche banks and assist the government in greater economic and policy issues.

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I. Introduction

The banking sector is right now believed to be in the 'consolidation - workout' stage. The Indian economy is becoming a 'merging' economy in the pursuit of an 'emerging' economy.

A merger of banks is not a new phenomenon but has been chatter of the banking sector at present as we are seeing more and more amalgamations these days. Naturally, experts and scholars in the field are trying to find out what is the driving force behind the mergers of the banks.

Many private & public sector banks in the past have joined hands to come & serve as one strong team. However, there has been a broader and continuous discussion regarding what it has in it for all of us. The topic has been raised for discussion for one more important reason, that banks are the backbone of any financial sector & their role and the way they function is immensely important in

fiscal stability and for the development of an economy like that of India. The health of the banking sector is a key reflector of the health of the economy, too.

II. Literature review

There have been some studies that particularly tackle this issue. Kumari, R. (2019) finds that due to multinational players in the field, banks in India, both public and private, face intense competition and the emergence of e-commerce and online banking has made small banks difficult to survive. As a result, she concludes, mergers and acquisitions are "the order of the day". Similarly, Kaleichelvan (2015) has looked at the M&A activity in the banking industry during the period 1993-94 – 2004- 05. Anand, M., & Singh, J. (2008) studied the impact of the merger on the shareholders of five banks: Times Bank with the HDFC Bank, the Bank of Madurai with the ICICI Bank, the ICICI Ltd with the ICICI Bank, the Global Trust Bank with the Oriental Bank of Commerce and the Bank of Punjab with the Centurion Bank. The study revealed that the announcement of the merger of banks had a significantly positive impact on shareholders' wealth. Sony, K. & Kumar, G. (2010) analyzed the strategic and financial similarities of merged Banks and relevant financial variables of respective banks and found that only private sector banks were in favor of a voluntary merger.

Khan, A. A. (2011) explored various motivations for a merger and acquisitions in the Indian banking sector, and the result of his study indicated that the banks have been positively affected by merging and acquisition. These results also suggested that merged banks could obtain efficiency and gains, and could pass the benefits to the equity shareholders mainly in the form of a dividend. Devarajappa, S. (2012) explored various motives for a merger in the Indian banking industry. The study also compared pre and post-merger financial performance of merged banks with the help of financial parameters like Gross Profit margin, Net Profit margin, operating Profit margin, Return on Capital Employed, Return on Equity, and Debt Equity Ratio. The study indicated that the banks had experienced a positive effect of merging.

III. Objective & Methods

The main objective of this paper is to analyze the effect of mergers of banks on the health of the banking sector and ultimately its impact on the Indian economy. We situate our arguments based on the data collected from various online articles, newspapers, research papers, books, reports, and so forth.

V. Discussion/Argument

There is no point for banks with different identities in targeting the same customer, that too, in a similar market with similar offerings. Hence the idea of consolidation attracts attention. This explains as to why the Government of India is focusing on reducing the number of Public Sector Banks (PSBs) in India. The Economic Survey of 2015-16 highlighted and suggested a *4R strategy* - *Recognition, Recapitalization, Resolution & Reform*. While the government has already introduced a number of schemes, laws and policies under the first 3Rs, the government under the 'Reform'

measures is supporting and following the idea of mergers is it in its own sector or the private sector.

Another relevant observation that can be made is of the '*synergistic effect*'. This can be explained through the merger of Dena Bank, Bank of Baroda & Vijaya bank. The dominance of Bank of Baroda in the western & northern regions and that of Vijaya bank in the southern region plus Dena bank's expertise in the MSME sector; together brought synergy in its operations. After the merger, the synergy effect was observed in terms of the geographical reach of more than 9,500 branches, and more than 13400 ATMs, 120 Million customers, and 85000 employees. After the merger, the entity has a deposit of Rs. 8.75 lakhs Crore and advances of Rs. 6.25 Lakhs Crore (The Economic Times 2019).

Another similar advantage is of '*economies of scale*'. Where there are many branches of individual banks, after the merger, they can be rationalized. Here a question arises regarding the job security of the employees. Of course, the banks do not increase the number of employees to handle the reduced number of branches. So where will the laid off or unemployed employees go? Although the government ostensibly claims to protect the interests of the affected employees, still we've seen in the case of merger of SBI & its 5 associates where around 4000 employees were forced to opt for a VRS (*Voluntary Retirement Scheme*). This is the prime reason why trade unions oppose such arrangements (Vikraman & Mathew 2017).

While mergers bring synergies at one side, there is a big challenge of *management of change* that awaits the managers. Before the merger, the entities had a unique set of operational guidelines, culture & work ethics. After the amalgamation, there will be, of course, a single, unified entity on the external front but internally there are bound to be several differences within the firm in terms of work culture, beliefs & ethos of the amalgamating entities. And it certainly takes time & effort for harmonization and integration of such diversities and differences. Managing such changes is a challenge in itself yet important step in ensuring that the amalgamated entity doesn't suffer in the end due to disagreement.

The other point is, to become a '*stronger bank*' the unified entity might subsume the sickness & limitations of weaker banks and exploit their growth potential. One relevant example would be of HDFC - the 2nd largest private sector lender bank of India with a total balance sheet of Rs. 8,95,653 Crore, and deposits of Rs 6,71,376 Crore. The company had a market capitalization of Rs. 4, 53,421 Crore (\$70.57 billion) on Sept. 05, 2017, after SBI climbed to this title through a series of acquisitions. Another example would be seen in the merger of SBI with its 5 associates and the Bhartiya Mahila Bank which made SBI the largest and stronger bank of India. Even the government's intention through a number of mergers like the recent one merger of 10 PSBs into four 'big banks' (w.e.f. April 2020) is to get them listed into the list of 'global-sized banks' in the Indian economy, which reflects India's aspiration to be a \$5 trillion economy (by GDP). This is also shown in table 1.1.

Table 1.1

10 PSB's	Effect of merger on bank
Punjab National Bank, Oriental Bank of Commerce and United Bank	2 nd largest PSB with ₹17.94 lakhs crore businesses and 11437 branches.
Canara Bank and Syndicate banks	4 th largest PSB with 15.2 lakhs crore business, 10,391 branches, 12829 ATMs, and 91,685 employees.
Union Bank of India, Andhra Bank, and Corporation Bank	5 th largest PSB with a business of ₹14.6 lakhs crore.
Indian Bank and Allahabad	7 th largest PSB with ₹8.08 lakhs crore business, 6,060 branches, 2870 ATMs and 9000 employees.

Source: Indiatvnews (2020) and Jagran Josh(2019)

But it is worth being careful to the fact that weaknesses of the weaker banks do not pull down the stronger ones, risking the stability of the economy. The suggestion can be exemplified through the merger of SBI with its 5 associates where after the merger the NPA of SBI was more than the individual aggregate & SBI reported losses for the first time in the decade in its quarterly results.

The *Raghuram Rajan Committee* also emphasized this in its report that mergers which are basically entered into to cover the flaws of the weaker banks do not result in *Bigger Weaker Banks*; the consequences of which will be worse than before.

As previously mentioned, amalgamations bring relief for the RBI also. It can better concentrate its efforts on the supervision of niche banks and assist the government in policy and greater economic issues.

The *NPA nodus* also gets checked through mergers. In fact, the recent Financial Stability Reports of the RBI reveal that there has been a growth in credit creation & a decline, although minimal in the NPAs. But one must remember that the arrangement doesn't uproot the NPA problem completely.

Mergers undoubtedly open an opportunity for funding for various budding developmental projects as financial resources get multiplied. It is however important to check that mergers do not hamper the healthy competition of the market and such arrangements do not lead to cartelization of Interest rates.

VI. What is the way forward?

It is important to emphasize that the government needs to improve on the implementation part of the Insolvency & Bankruptcy Code. It's been seen that even after many of its implementation, only a few cases have been resolved. Moreover, the 'recovery' mechanism under the IBC needs to be improved.

Various committees associated with the issue point out that mergers are a way for banks to resolve the NPA menace. Even the RBI and the government seem to take more of the 'curative' measures rather than being preventive. So there's a need of a

better mechanism that provides banks an easy access to the most sought-after expertise on productive avenues so that they don't get stuck in loss-making assets at the first instance; and if any such thing happens, banks get the support and authority to get it resolved as soon as possible.

In the case of PSBs, more autonomy must be given to the RBI and the Boards of such PSBs. Since the government is the major stakeholder in such banks, RBI finds it difficult to exercise its control on them because the PSBs are ultimately answerable to the government, not the RBI. This is similar to what was recommended by the Arvind Mehta Committee. Also, the boards of PSBs must have the authority to decide on issues like mergers and not the government imposing its decision on them.

VII. Conclusions

In this article we argue that mergers of banks in India, which is a consolidation of the competencies, culture, and shortcomings of different entities is likely to be a boon for the health of the banking sector and also to the economy as a whole. A merger is helpful in enhancing performance by offsetting weaknesses of a bank. As witnessed in several examples, bank mergers also result in an increased use of technological tools. The synergy brought together through merging also helps in terms of customer reach, tools of operations, technology and diversified business for each amalgamating bank. This altogether helps build stronger financial sector. Some private banks used mergers as strategic tools for expanding their horizons, and they continue to do so. In addition, merging and acquisition render huge potential in rural markets of India, which is not yet explored by the major banks of India.

Notes on Contributors

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